

Mixed-ligand Complexes of Magnesium and Calcium

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Magnesium and calcium are biologically important metals¹. A number of mixed complexes Mg and Ca have been reported recently². The present communication reports the synthesis and characterisation of mixed-ligand complexes of general formula [ML.HL'], where M=Mg or Ca; L=deprotonated *o*-nitrophenol (ONP), salicylaldehyde (SalH), salicylic acid (SalA), anthranilic acid (anth) or 8-hydroxyquinolene (8Hq); HL'=unideprotonated salicylidene *o*-aminophenol (Salcap).

Results and Discussion

Analytical data (Table 1) suggest the general

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd./ (Colour)	Melting/ Decomp. temp. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
		Mg/Ca	C	H	N
[(H.Saloap = HL)] (Orange)	160d	—	74.12 (73.23)	4.82 (5.16)	6.42 (6.57)
[Mg(ONP).L] (Yellow)	278d	6.22 (6.41)	62.82 (60.98)	3.76 (4.01)	7.21 (7.48)
[Mg(SalH).L] (Light yellow)	>300	6.44 (6.72)	65.52 (67.03)	5.10 (4.74)	3.54 (3.91)
[Mg(SalA).L] (Light pink)	>300	6.36 (6.41)	63.52 (64.17)	4.95 (4.54)	3.26 (3.74)
[Mg(anth).L] (Gray)	230d	6.18 (6.43)	63.30 (64.34)	4.23 (4.82)	7.83 (7.51)
[Mg(8HQ).L] (Light yellow)	>300	6.28 (6.30)	70.01 (69.29)	4.94 (4.72)	7.27 (7.35)
[Ca(ONP).L] (Deep orange)	219d	10.12 (10.23)	59.11 (58.31)	4.01 (3.84)	7.26 (7.16)
[Ca(SalH).L] (Orange)	220d	10.62 (10.72)	64.35 (64.17)	4.61 (4.54)	3.68 (3.74)
[Ca(SalA).L] (Light yellow)	245d	10.01 (10.25)	60.92 (61.54)	4.73 (4.36)	3.41 (3.59)
[Ca(anth).L] (Brown)	220d	9.86 (10.33)	61.86 (61.70)	4.93 (4.62)	6.84 (7.20)

formula of the complexes as [ML.HL'], indicating the reaction,

The ν_{C-N} band at 1 640 cm^{-1} in the spectra of H.Saloap, has been found to undergo a low frequency shift by about 10–30 cm^{-1} in the complexes, suggesting coordination of saloap through the azomethine group. The ν_{OH} bands of H.Saloap appearing at ~ 3 400, 3 200 and 2 750 cm^{-1} (OH to be H-bonded) remain almost in the same positions in the complexes. Most likely one of the two OH groups of H.Saloap is coordinated to the metal while the other one gets deprotonated in the complexes.

Infrared spectra of the complexes also suggest the coordination of additional donor groups in the primary ligands, such as NO_2 (1 560, 1 550), CHO (1 675, 1 695), OH (3 520, 3 510) and NH (3 340, 3400 cm^{-1} for Mg and Ca complexes, respectively) in ONP, SalH, SalA, anth, respectively, to the metal. Thus, chelate rings are formed by both primary and secondary ligands. The probable structure of the complexes shown in Fig. 1.

Experimental

Mg/Ca salts of different organic acids were prepared by the interaction of metal hydroxide and organic acids in 1 : 2 mole ratio in acetone medium and were found to have ML_2 composition.

Salicylidene *o*-aminophenol was prepared by stirring the mixture of *o*-aminophenol (4.36 g) and salicylaldehyde (4.3 ml) in absolute ethanol

NOTES

Fig. 1.

(~50 ml) for 1 h and the resulting solid was washed with ethanol and dried at 100°.

The mixed complexes were prepared by refluxing a suspension of Mg/Ca salt of the primary ligand (ONP, SalH, SalA, etc.) in acetone with salicylidene *o*-aminophenol (in 1:1 mole ratio), on a hot-plate for 1 h. The resulting solids were washed with the solvent and dried at 100°.

References

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